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The Study of Old Norse Grammatical Literature c. 2000-2024

Abstract: This article offers a critical survey of scholarship on Old Norse grammatical literature from approximately 2000 to 2024, proposing a broader and more integrative conception of *grammatica* than prior reviews. Extending beyond the four canonical grammatical treatises, it includes works such as Snorri Sturluson's *Edda*, *Litla Skálda*, and the Icelandic Rune Poem, thereby recontextualizing the intellectual landscape of medieval Icelandic philology. Particular attention is given to recent methodological shifts emphasizing empirical scrutiny, source analysis, and cross-disciplinary testing of hypotheses. Case studies illustrate how Latin grammatical models were selectively appropriated and transformed within a vernacular framework, challenging conventional narratives of cultural dependence. This re-evaluation not only enriches our understanding of the transmission and function of grammatical knowledge in the North but also underscores the originality and analytical depth of Icelandic scholarly production in the high and late Middle Ages.

Keywords: Old Norse, Grammatical treatises, Snorri Sturluson, Latin-Norse intellectual exchange, Medieval Scandinavian scholarship

Riassunto: Questo articolo offre una panoramica critica degli studi sulla letteratura grammaticale norrena dal 2000 al 2024 circa, proponendo una concezione della grammatica più ampia e integrativa rispetto alle precedenti recensioni. Andando oltre i quattro trattati grammaticali canonici, include opere come l'Edda di Snorri Sturluson, Litla Skálda e il Poema runico islandese, ricollocando così nel contesto il panorama intellettuale della filologia islandese medievale. Particolare attenzione è riservata ai recenti cambiamenti metodologici che enfatizzano l'analisi empirica, l'analisi delle fonti e la verifica interdisciplinare delle ipotesi. Casi di studio illustrano come i modelli grammaticali latini siano stati selettivamente appropriati e trasformati all'interno di un quadro vernacolare, sfidando le narrazioni convenzionali della dipendenza culturale. Questa rivalutazione non solo arricchisce la nostra comprensione della trasmissione e della funzione della conoscenza grammaticale nel Nord, ma sottolinea anche l'originalità e la profondità analitica della produzione accademica islandese nell'alto e tardo Medioevo.

Parole chiave: norreno antico, trattati grammaticali, Snorri Sturluson, scambi intellettuali tra latino e norreno, studi medievali scandinavi

In 2007, Fabrizio Raschellà published an overview of scholarship on Old Icelandic grammatical literature in the period 1983-2005. In one sense, the present article may be seen as a continuation of Raschellà's chapter. There are,

however, some differences between the two. Raschellà used a narrower definition of grammatical literature, confining it to the four so-called grammatical treatises. This is a valid definition, but it does not allow us to bring out the commonalities with other texts more or less loosely related to medieval grammatical study. Instead, I here define medieval *grammatica* more inclusively, as the study of script and language governed by rules, including poetic language. The present overview therefore covers a greater range of texts, including Snorri's *Edda*, which continues to attract considerable scholarly interest. I also attempt some evaluation of the empirical underpinnings of the arguments presented, in the hope that this may prove useful to readers. These choices imply that the overview must be selective. As a principle of selection, I have prioritised studies that in a relatively concrete manner aim to provide us with new or more secure knowledge about texts belonging to the Old Norse grammatical corpus. I pay less attention to general overviews, as well as studies emphasising scholarly perspectives more than the testing of hypotheses against the sources¹. Even taking this limitation into account, I readily confess that I may have overlooked valuable contributions and that other selections of studies and topics could have been equally valuable.

The cutting-off point of 2000 should be understood as approximate, and at times I include publications as far back as the 1980s, due to their connections to later scholarship. In the following, I first treat the grammatical treatises, then Snorri's *Edda* and finally poetry.

1. The Grammatical Treatises

The four so-called grammatical treatises have been numbered according to their order of appearance in the manuscript containing them all, Codex Wormianus (AM 242 fol., c. 1350). A fragment of a fifth treatise, now commonly referred to as the Fifth Grammatical Treatise, is found in AM 748 1b 4to (early fourteenth century). The conventional Anglophone abbreviations for the four grammatical treatises are *FiGT*, *SGT*, *ThGT* and *FoGT*, but if the fifth is included, this results in two *FiGTs*, and I therefore use 1GT, 2GT, etc.

¹ One succinct overview not treated below yet worthy of particular mention is Engesland's forthcoming chapter on Old Norse and medieval Irish grammatical literature. It is the first of its kind, and it conveys the state of the art within both branches of scholarship. As such is likely to prove very useful to scholars.

1.1. *IGT*

IGT is generally seen as a unique witness to Old Norse phonology at an early date, *c.* 1150. As such, the text had benefitted from detailed studies and editions well before 2000, notably those by Anne Holtsmark and Hreinn Benediktsson (Holtsmark 1936; Hreinn Benediktsson (ed.) 1972). In recent decades, I think it fair to say that *IGT* often serves as a point of reference, but that advances in our understanding of the text itself have been relatively modest.

The first contribution to be discussed has to do with the First Grammarian's views on language, and it may require some introduction. When faced with the First Grammarian's analyses, the question «how could he be so good?» almost inevitably reports itself. In particular, the high quality of the First Grammarian's phonological analysis of the vernacular is unique for its time. Irish bardic tracts postdating *IGT* by perhaps two centuries sometimes rival its precision, but they lack its analytical coherence (Engesland, forthcoming). Other medieval vernacular grammars come nowhere near. Composed at a time when the Norse area was acquiring the basics of Latin learned discourse, this anomaly cannot easily be explained by recourse to that tradition. Comparison to the bardic tracts suggests that the explanation primarily lies in the poetic tradition, since at such an early date, Old Norse skaldic and Irish syllabic poetry were the two medieval literary forms where precise phonological distinctions mattered the most. In addition, the composition of traditional poetry was an attractive career path in both societies.

Still, a successful phonological description takes more than practical skill in language and poetry. It requires an apt analytical framework, and in the case of the First Grammarian, this would involve adapting Latin models to the needs of Old Norse. The Old Norse vowel inventory would have been particularly challenging, as it comprised nine vowels, all of which could be either long or short, oral or nasal. Scholars have pointed to possible sources of inspiration to the First Grammarian's analysis, but the fact remains that the feature of nasality is irrelevant to both Latin *differentiae* and skaldic rhymes. Whatever his sources of inspiration, it is thus clear that the First Grammarian was a great innovator and an acute analyst.

This is where an article by Gunnar Harðarson (1999; *idem*, 2016a: 48) enters the equation. As Gunnar notes, the First Grammarian sees Norse and English as fundamentally the same language, having been separated by language change. He does not refer to the standard medieval explanation of the existence of different languages, which was the division of tongues at the Tower of Babel. This deviation from the standard model demonstrates his propensity to draw conclusions from empirical observation, rather than adhering to convention. As such, Gunnar's analysis allows us to glimpse a crucial characteristic of the individual that produced such an acute analysis, as opposed to the general preconditions of

his cultural background. After all, if a text stands out within its cultural setting, it is reasonable to expect that some characteristic set its author apart from others within that setting. By all appearances, the First Grammarian combined a sense of entitlement to draw independent conclusions with an unusually developed analytical capacity.

Another contribution relates to whether the First Grammarian does or does not criticise the use of runes as a book script. It is a longstanding perception that although 1GT twice uses the word *rúnar* ‘runes’, the author is not actually referring to runes, but only to letters. The present author has shown, however, that this view is due to a long tradition of mistranslations, ultimately harking back to Latin translations of the nineteenth century (Males 2021a). Since Latin has no words for runes, *litterae* or *characteres* were used, and when the Latin translations were later consulted for translation into modern languages, the normal meaning of *litterae* and *characteres* gave rise to the translation ‘letters’ rather than ‘runes’. This is thus a translation error resulting from Latin semantic contamination. In fact, the First Grammarian did criticise the imprecision of the runes. It may seem surprising that he would do so at a time when the runes were again becoming more precise, due to the addition of a range of disambiguating signs. Things were different in the grammatical discourse, however. In the discussion of poetry below, we shall see that the imprecise 16-character inventory had been promoted in Iceland only decades before 1GT. The First Grammarian’s reaction thus makes sense as part of the learned discourse of his day.

1.2. 2GT

Regarding 2GT, the signal achievement is still Fabrizio Raschellà’s edition of 1982. It may be noted, however, that Raschellà focuses on the author’s text and leaves interesting additions to it in Codex Wormianus without comment. 2GT prompted the Wormianus redactor to envision the possibility of plotting all the world’s letters / phonemes into a single grid – a kind of IPA *ante litteram* if you will – which to his exegetical mind suggested the possibility of recovering the prelapsarian language of Adam or something like it. As such, the redactor’s additions are an interesting source to theo-grammatical thought in an Icelandic monastic context. The present author has now edited these with translation and commentary, and Jonas Wellendorf has explored additions by the same redactor to the prologue of Snorri’s *Edda* (Males 2020: 279-285, 316-319; Wellendorf 2013).

1.3. 3GT

Scholarship on 3GT has seen considerable advances in the period, mainly regarding its sources, but Tarrin Wills also produced an edition of the first part of the treatise in his Ph.D. thesis of 2001. 3GT was composed by Snorri's nephew Óláfr Þórðarson around 1250. It is a translation of Priscian's *Institutiones I-II* and Donatus's *Barbarismus* (the third book of his *Ars maior*). The translation was also very much an adaptation, however, as illustrated by the fact that in parts of the discussion of letters in his translation from Priscian, Óláfr uses runes instead of letters, and in the translation of *Barbarismus*, he supplants Latin hexameter verses with skaldic poetry.

A number of sources have been identified for both parts of 3GT. I begin with the first part. Kari Ellen Gade has demonstrated that the source is Priscian's *Institutiones* rather than *Excerptiones de Prisciano*, which has sometimes been suggested (Gade 2007). More interestingly, perhaps, Gade also convincingly argues that Óláfr consulted Ælfric's *Excerptiones de arte grammatica anglice* in his work. She notes striking similarities in terminology and supports her observations by reference to an Icelandic fragment of a translation from Ælfric's *Excerptiones*, dating to c. 1400. Since this text must presumably have reached Iceland when Old English was still studied in England, we arrive at an *ante quem* c. 1200-1250, making Gade's hypothesis highly plausible.

In 2015, Richard Cole identified another source-type used by Óláfr, as well as by the First Grammarian (Cole 2015: 75-85). Cole's finding is easily overlooked by the scholar of grammatical literature, being "hidden" in his thesis on the perception of Jews in Old Norse literature. Lists of different scripts, their names and sound equivalents were widespread from the Carolingian period onwards, and such a list, containing Greek and Hebrew letters, names and values, is found in the Icelandic manuscript AM 685 d 4to 30v-31r (fifteenth century). As far as I am aware, Cole first brought this testimony into the discussion of 1GT and 3GT². There are clear indications in both treatises that their authors consulted some such list. The precise background to Óláfr's knowledge of Hebrew diacritics (so-called *matres lectionis*) remains a mystery, however³.

Kate Heslop has noted that the use of the term *consonantia* in the *Third Grammatical Treatise* in tandem with the quotation of a couplet of rhythmical poetry seems to indicate influence from the contemporary Latin discourse on such poetry (Heslop 2022: 172-73). She also argues for similar influences on the *Second*

² Cole mentions no scholar who discusses it, and the manuscript is not included in Holtmark's excellent study of 1GT's intellectual background (perhaps unsurprisingly, since Holtmark focuses on an earlier period; Holtmark 1936: 72, 113-115).

³ The present author has explored the topic further, also discussing lists of scripts containing runes, which are not included in Cole's study (Males 2020: 182-185).

Grammatical Treatise and *Háttatal* (Heslop 2022: 173-174, 182). This is of general interest for the discourse on poetry in Old Norse grammatical literature, since Latin rhythmical poetry focused on syllable count and end-rhymes. Both of these are apt to confuse the analysis of Old Norse poetry, with its variable syllable count and internal rhymes adhering to different principles than Latin rhymes. Heslop's observations thus serve to elucidate some of the challenges facing the authors of the grammatical treatises when adapting Latin-based analyses to their object of study.

Regarding the second part of 3GT, the adaptation of the *Barbarismus* to skaldic stylistics called for considerable ingenuity, and identifying which commentary to Donatus Óláfr used is therefore of interest for understanding his translation strategies. In 1993 and 1999, Valeria Micillo noted particular affinities between 3GT and three commentaries composed by Irish *peregrini* on the continent in the ninth century. Since Óláfr presumably used one main source rather than three, however, the question of his exemplar did not find a fully satisfactory answer through Micillo's studies. In a pilot study of 2018, the present author noted that an unedited commentary drawing on the three discussed by Micillo seemed to contain all relevant material. The topic was explored in detail by Victor Frans in 2019. Frans also included a preliminary edition of the text, whose scholarly name ought probably, at least for the time being, be *Ars Brugensis*. Although still in the format of an unedited MA thesis, Frans's treatment is now the state of the art, and there can be little doubt that Óláfr's source has been identified. Using Frans's edition, source and target text can now be compared, an asset used by Matteo Tarsi in his study of Latin versus native terminology in 3GT (Tarsi 2020).

Frans also evaluated a hypothesis presented by Tarrin Wills in 2017, namely that Óláfr in addition to a commentary consulted the *Aeneid* directly. Frans noted that at least in one instance, this may indeed to be the case, although the similarities are somewhat general in nature, and chance may thus be an equally plausible explanation (Frans 2019, 48). If Óláfr did consult the *Aeneid*, *Ars Brugensis* would have been helpful, since unlike other commentaries that have been discussed, it tends to note from which book in the *Aeneid* a quotation is taken (Frans 2019, 47-48).

Perhaps more importantly from an educational perspective, Frans also uncovered fundamental components of Óláfr's translation strategy. Frans notes that for the structure of the treatise, Óláfr mainly followed Alexander de Villa Dei's *Doctrinale*, but for content, he followed Donatus and the newly identified commentary (Frans 2019: 69, 74). The *Doctrinale* was widely used in Latin teaching during the thirteenth century and later, but while having the benefit that it is designed to be learned by heart, it is often obscure and in need of a teacher's elucidation. Donatus with commentary provides the necessary explanations. In other words, while 3GT mainly translates Donatus, it is nonetheless adapted to serve as a tool for the study of the *Doctrinale*. The apparently traditionalist move of transforming Donatus's

text into a treatise on skaldic poetry thus turns out, in the end, also to constitute an act of modernisation, adapting the source to the standards of thirteenth-century Latin education.

The adaptation to the *Doctrinale* has some implications for the discussion of whether Óláfr hosted a school or not. In *Porgils saga skarða*, we read about the priest Þorsteinn tittlingr that «Hann hafði verið til kennslu í Stafaholti með Óláfi Þórðarsyni» ‘He had been studying / teaching in Stafholt with Óláfr Þórðarson’⁴. In a 1910 article, Finnur Jónsson took this as evidence that Óláfr hosted a school in Stafholt (Finnur Jónsson 1910: 195-196). Most subsequent scholars have accepted this, but in 2023, Þórgunnur Snædal argued that there would have been no reason to mention only one of the students instead of the school, had such a school existed (Þórgunnur Snædal 2023: 62). This is a reasonable argument, but in a contemporary saga, the author may well have chosen to leave out things that were well known, and in any event, some teaching apparently took place «in Stafholt with Óláfr Þórðarson». Frans’s analysis allows us to flesh out the picture. Adapting Donatus to an updated curriculum seems a considerable overkill for the teaching of a single pupil, and whatever came of Óláfr’s ambitions, he thus apparently had some kind of school setting in mind. The absence of the mention of a school may be due to the fact that, as Ryder Patzuk-Russell notes, the word *skóli* is not used of secular centres of learning (Patzuk-Russell 2021: 76).

Apart from these advances relating to Óláfr’s sources and his use of them, a linguistic point has seen some debate based on 3GT. Klaus Johan Myrvoll and Trygve Skomedal have argued that the grammatical terminology known to Óláfr offered no means unambiguously to refer to tonal differences, and since the accents inherited from Greek had no practical value for the description of Old Norse, Óláfr instead used them to refer to tone (Myrvoll and Skomedal 2010). The strongest indication to this effect lies in the authors’ analysis of the form *bænum*, where Óláfr states that one may make an error in accent. Myrvoll and Skomedal argue that Óláfr is here referring to tone, since depending on the toneme, this form may either represent *bæ-num*, definite dative singular of *bær* ‘farm’, or *bæn-um*, dative plural of *bæn* ‘prayer’. If their analysis is correct, this is a rare piece of evidence of tonal distinctions in Old Icelandic. Exploring the topic further, Kristján Árnason and Haukur Þorgeirsson have drawn evidence from late *dróttkvætt* poetry into the evaluation, which turns out to be consistent with the hypothesis (although the authors stress that the distinction was probably not yet systemic; Kristján Árnason and Haukur Þorgeirsson 2017: 57). By contrast, Jón Axel Harðarson argues that Óláfr is referring to word division rather than tone, just as he does in his preceding example, and he adduces manuscript evidence in support of the analysis of

⁴ Most have taken this to mean that he was studying, but as Guðrún Nordal notes, it may also mean that he was a teacher (Guðrún Nordal 2001: 181).

bæ-num as two words (Jón Axel Harðarson 2016: 69-71). The only manuscript mentioned is very early and contains yet earlier material, however, and the argument would have been stronger if backed up by contemporary evidence. Myrvoll and Skomedal's hypothesis would thus appear to be better able to explain the data so far presented, although Jón Axel's observations are valid and invite caution⁵.

1.4. 4GT

4GT has been edited anew in 2014 by Margaret Clunies Ross and Jonas Wellendorf. This is a very useful edition, for the first time providing a translation, as well as an accessible overview of the author's use of the *Doctinale* and *Graecismus*. It also includes an excellent discussion of the anonymous stanzas, most of which may be assumed to be the author's own. In Snorri's *Edda*, such stanzas are the exception, and they are relatively rare also in 3GT. In 4GT, by contrast, 47 of 62 stanzas are anonymous (Clunies Ross – Wellendorf 2014: xlv, xlix-l). Clunies Ross and Wellendorf explore possible reasons for this difference, their main and highly plausible hypothesis being that this is due to the treatise's monastic context. Its author wished to introduce a more exegetical style than what was available in earlier poetry, which might be well received by his brethren and prove useful for the composition of religious verse. Overall, this edition is a milestone for the study of monastic grammatical activity and poetics in the fourteenth century.

1.5. 5GT

This treatise has led a marginal existence in scholarly literature. It is to be counted among the merits of Guðrún Nordal's 2001 *Tools of Literacy* that she there treated 5GT alongside the other grammatical treatises, and the same may be said of *Litla Skálda*, which Guðrún discusses in tandem with Snorri's *Edda* (Guðrún Nordal 2001: 41-72). In key nineteenth-century editions, these texts were edited together, but in the twentieth century, scholarship had increasingly moved in the direction of focusing on a "canon" of Snorri's *Edda* and 1-4GT. Guðrún's inclusive approach, taking its starting point in the manuscripts, is more useful for delineating the development of grammatical thought, and the same may be said of her inclusion of poetic precursors, to be further discussed below.

⁵ During the final preparation of this manuscript, Haukur Þorgeirsson kindly allowed me to read a forthcoming article by Sólveig Hilmarsdóttir and himself. The article offers further support for the tonal hypothesis. In addition, it addresses other topics discussed above, for instance by drawing on Frans's edition of *Ars Brugensis*. I therefore wish to draw attention to the article, even though I have been unable to integrate it into the larger discussion above.

Being a fragment of a little over eight lines, the limited scholarly attention accorded to 5GT is understandable, but on closer inspection, the treatise turns out to be an interesting hybrid text. In 2017, the present author published the first closer analysis of 5GT since 1884, concluding that there is internal evidence in support of the manuscript's attribution of the treatise to Óláfr Þórðarson. He also noted that unlike Snorri's *Edda*, 5GT focuses on features central to Latin grammatical discourse, whereas in contradistinction to corresponding parts of 3GT, 5GT does not use Latin, but rather native terminology that has apparently been invented for the occasion. For this and other reasons discussed in the study, 5GT seems to have been Óláfr's first attempt at composing a different kind of treatise than that of his uncle. These observations allow us to observe an intellectual development from Snorri's *Edda* to 5GT and finally to 3GT. When treating Snorri and his nephews Óláfr and Sturla, whose collective importance for Old Norse literature may without exaggeration be called immeasurable, it is of interest to note that Óláfr seems actively to have sought ways to stake a claim for himself by means of complementary distribution. Snorri was the nativist vernacular grammarian, who presented even Latin-derived ideals as sanctioned by local tradition (see below). By contrast, Óláfr would demonstrate that the taxonomy of Latin *grammatica* was applicable to the native tradition. Apparently, his detachment from his uncle's approach happened gradually. At first, Óláfr aimed for nativising terminology à la Snorri (5GT), but subsequently, he seems to have realised that his relatively high level of latinity could serve as an asset in his attempts to become an authority in his own right, and he thus embraced Latin terminology in 3GT. Of course, this interpretation of Óláfr's incentives must remain speculative, but whatever its merits, it may serve to illustrate that 5GT has more to offer for our interpretation of Sturlung *grammatica* than first meets the eye.

2. Snorri's *Edda*

Snorri's *Edda* is a complex work inviting exploration among numerous parameters. For clarity, I introduce each topic below in bold letters.

Religious perspectives. The overall religious perspective of Snorri's *Edda* is a point of some contention (Wellendorf 2018: 84-108). Heinrich Beck claimed that Snorri operated with «analogy», under the influence of the *Canones* of the Fourth Lateran Council (1215), and Beck's view has been endorsed by Jan Alexander van Nahl (Beck 1994; van Nahl 2013a, 2013b and 2015). As Gunnar Harðarson notes, however, arguments from analogy are traditional within Christian thinking (Gunnar Harðarson 2016b: 79-80). Indeed, there is a case to be made that they are universal (Lakoff and Johnson 1980). As such, it seems doubtful that an author's recourse to analogical reasoning, such as highlighting similarities and

differences between paganism and Christianity, can convincingly be traced to a particular source such as the *Canones*. This would have required more marked and cogent correspondences, such as parallels in phrasing or specific interpretative techniques, which is not forthcoming in Beck's and van Nahl's publications on the topic.

In his 2018 monograph, Jonas Wellendorf discusses Beck's analysis, as well as that proposed by Anne Holtsmark (1964), where she argued that Snorri presents the gods as demons. In contrast to both scholars, Wellendorf notes that euhemerism is the only explicit explanation of Old Norse paganism presented in Snorri's *Edda*. Unlike Holtsmark, Wellendorf finds no traces of demonology in Snorri's *Edda*, and he thus arrives at euhemerism as the main interpretive framework. He does so by means of a balanced evaluation of probabilities based on the text under study as well as comparison with others where a demonological perspective is clearly present.

Snorri's *Edda* and *Litla Skálda*. When Guðrún Nordal published her 2001 monograph, the text known as *Litla Skálda* had been largely ignored by scholars for a long time. This is a treatise on kennings and *heiti*, which early philologists took to be a digest of *Skáldskaparmál*. Guðrún included *Litla Skálda* in her study, focusing primarily on its interplay with Snorri's *Edda* in the manuscripts AM 748 Ib 4to and AM 757 a 4to. She also noted, however, that it discusses several kenning types not found in *Skáldskaparmál*, meaning that it cannot simply be a digest of that text (Guðrún Nordal 2001: 57-66; cf. Males 2020: 133).

In 2009 Judith Jesch continued the discussion, exploring the possibility that *Litla Skálda* may have been composed in the Orkneys, as suggested by some similarities to *Háttalykill* (Jesch 2009). If so, it seems likely that it is slightly older than Snorri's *Edda*, based on what we know of literary activities in Orkney. Later, Inger Helene Solvin noted in her MA thesis that the progression of topics in *Litla Skálda* is associative rather than systematic (Solvin 2015: 14-25). Consider, for instance, the following quotation:

[...] lagvápn má kalla fiska heitum ok orma, ok kenna við herklæði ok hlífar, sár eða blóð. Blóð er kallað sjóar heitum ok vatna, ok kent við hræ eða ben, sár eða undir. Sjó má kalla [...] (Finnur Jónsson 1931: 256)

[[...] piercing weapons may be called by the names of fishes and snakes, and be defined by armour and shields, wounds or *blood*. *Blood* is called by the names of the *sea* and bodies of water, and defined by carrion or injuries, wounds or gashes. The *sea* may be called [...]]

The section on weapons includes a mention of blood, which prompted the author to treat that topic, and in so doing, he mentioned the sea, which then became the following topic, etc. This fundamental difference between *Litla Skálda*'s associative and Snorri's systematic approach will become relevant below.

In 2020, the present author took his starting point in the observations presented by Guðrún, Jesch and Solvin in order to explore whether Snorri used *Litla Skálda* in his work (Males 2020: 133-47). As it turns out, there are signs of intertextual influence between the two texts, spread over all three sections of *Litla Skálda* (Males 2020: 140-144). Furthermore, as noted above, the progression of topics in *Litla Skálda* is associative, whereas *Skáldskaparmál* operates with clear semantic categories: first come kennings for gods and poetry (the latter being associated with Óðinn), then nature, then humans, then gold, then battle, etc. It is easy to see how the incoherent presentation of *Litla Skálda* could have prompted an attempt at systematisation, but not how the excellent structure of *Skáldskaparmál* could disappear without a trace. Since the intertextual links are unambiguous, this probably means that *Litla Skálda* has influenced *Skáldskaparmál*, and additional features are most easily explained in the same manner (Males 2020: 145).

When combined with other observations, this conclusion has considerable implications for the twelfth-century background of thirteenth-century Icelandic grammatical discourse. In her study, Guðrún Nordal draws attention to the continuities between twelfth-century poetry and thirteenth-century grammatical treatises (Guðrún Nordal 2001, 117-195). In my 2020 book, I employ a new subdivision of mythological kennings into generic and complex ones and am thus able to demonstrate that the latter fell almost completely out of use in the eleventh century and were revived by ecclesiastical poets in the twelfth (Males 2020: 39-94). The same poets revived complex poetic diction overall, and chief among them was Einarr Skúlason (c. 1090-1160), who was also Snorri's main poetic source of inspiration in *Skáldskaparmál*. For *Háttatal*, Snorri's model was the poem *Háttalykill*, composed in the 1140s.

When *Litla Skálda* is introduced into this picture, the overall development becomes clear: Snorri's *Edda* was the apex of scholarly trends that had been gaining force for about a century prior to its composition. A progression of studies by Guðrún-Jesch-Solvin-Males, each involving the testing of some new parameters, thus allows us to discard the truism that Snorri's *Edda* was composed to save the skaldic art from extinction. Few would now embrace how Sigurður Nordal originally formulated this view, claiming that Snorri's aim was to arrest «the victorious advance of the Roman Church in Iceland» (Sigurður Nordal 1931: 12). Rather, the claim has won wider currency in Elias Wessén's less nationalistic formulation (Wessén 1940: 12-13, 30). Still, Snorri's rescue mission has remained a commonplace whose plausibility has gone unchallenged. In fact, the case turns out to be the opposite: skaldic poetry and scholarship were gaining ground, if not at the courts, then certainly in Icelandic learned discourse. Indeed, as Frans's study of the structural affinities between 3GT and the *Doctrinale* has shown, skaldic poetry would continue to find new applications even after Snorri, providing access to an updated Latin syllabus. Nostalgic notions of a lost golden age could not be more wrong.

The authorship of *Háttatal*. Another development in the scholarship on Snorri's *Edda* consists not so much an advance in its own right as in the re-evaluation of an important publication that has been omitted in recent standard editions. In 1929, Finnur Jónsson presented a range of strong arguments indicating that the commentary to *Háttatal* was composed by Snorri. In Anthony Faulkes' now standard edition of Snorri's *Edda*, this article was not consulted, and the same is true of the edition of *Háttatal* in *Skaldic Poetry of the Scandinavian Middle Ages*, being the new standard edition of skaldic poetry. As a result, the authorship there appears less certain than it really is, although in the event, both find Snorri to be the most likely author (Faulkes 2007: ix; Clunies Ross *et al.* 2007-: 3, 1095). In 2006, Jónas Kristjánsson published further observations in support of Finnur's view (Jónas Kristjánsson 2006: 111, 120-121), also not referenced in these editions. In 2020, the present author revisited Finnur's arguments and added some further indications to the same effect (Males 2020: 114-118). The hypothesis that Snorri is the author of the commentary, except perhaps parts of the commentary on stanza 8, has thus been subjected to considerable scrutiny and now appears quite solid.

Snorri's intellectual outlook. One challenge that has occupied scholars is Snorri's terminology. While Fabrizio Raschellà in particular has produced excellent overviews of the technical vocabulary of 1-4GT, Snorri's terminology is more elusive, being less indebted to Latin and in many instances apparently independent of such models. The potential pitfalls may be illustrated by two hypotheses on the background of the key concept of the *kenning*. In 1987, Margaret Clunies Ross argued that it was derived from religious discourse, whereas Mats Malm in 2009 saw it as influenced by the teaching of (Pseudo-)Ciceronian rhetoric (Clunies Ross 1987: 50-60; Malm 2009). Quite apart from the fact that this brand of rhetoric was most likely unknown in thirteenth-century Iceland, the recent identification of Snorri's use of *Litla Skálda* renders the search for a specific Latin model moot. In *Litla Skálda*, only the verbal phrase *kenna við* ('signify by means of reference to') is used, but not the corresponding noun *kenning*. Apparently, Snorri thought that the action of *kenna við* ought to have a name, as other figures do in grammatical discourse, and he thus adapted the meaning of the noun *kenning* 'perception, teaching' to that of the verbal phrase. We here see an organic development within Old Icelandic scholarship on poetry, not a calque on Latin. Of course, the impulse to create a technical terminology and to compose scholarly treatises was indebted to the Latin grammatical discourse, but the dynamics involved remained based on local traditions. This makes Snorri's terminology especially interesting, but also challenging. One of the complications involved is that scholars tend to expect a precise and consistent terminology, such as one may find in both modern and medieval grammar. This does not seem to be how the Old Norse poetic discourse operated, however, at least not prior to Snorri. For one thing, early Germanic metre is so complex that, even today, scholars have difficulties coming up with

a consistent terminology. The verses are ever-changing in remarkably complex patterns. This suggests that poets must have learned their trade by doing it, and apart from some terminology referring to alliterating staves, rhymes, etc., the key technical terms may well have been *right* and *wrong*.

It thus seems likely that in many instances, there was no terminology denoting concepts that seem key to us. In others, traditional terminology may have been based on other premises than the ones of mainstream grammatical discourse. Bianca Patria has identified an important instance of this in her analysis of the term *nýgerving* ‘new making, innovation’ (Patria 2022). In so doing, she has also related the term to what may be the most important stylistic driving force in the skaldic discourse: emulation.

Scholars have long grappled with Snorri’s use of the term *nýgerving*, since he seems to use it to refer both to the extension of a metaphor and to the substitution of one *heiti* for another. From the perspective of Greco-Roman, medieval and modern taxonomies alike, Snorri would thus appear to contradict himself. This grammatical tradition is based on formal description, however, and Patria hypothesised that Snorri’s term might instead be based on the dynamics of composition, as indicated by the semantics of the word (‘new making, innovation’). Testing her hypothesis against skaldic practice, Patria was able to show that Snorri’s use of the term is, in fact, consistent, if one allows for it to denote different surface realisations of the same underlying dynamic. By *nýgerving*, Snorri apparently means the extension of a metaphor or metonym beyond ordinary skaldic convention. This can be done by employing a *heiti* not used by previous poets or for instance by correlating a verb to the base-word of a kenning, so that if fire is a «dog of embers», it *bites* rather than *burns* its victims. Performing such innovations required knowledge of the entire skaldic canon, and it has become increasingly clear that this was required of the skalds⁶. Only by so doing could they innovate and thus achieve fame as gifted poetic craftsmen. Innovation was thus at the core of the skaldic enterprise. This may seem counterintuitive, since skaldic poetry is so conventionalised and traditional, but it was precisely for this reason that innovations within clearly set parameters was seen as a badge of honour.

As Patria notes, Snorri himself is partly to blame for the disinclination of later scholars to recognise the fundamental importance of innovation to the skaldic tradition. His kenning taxonomy in *Skáldskaparmál* was in one sense “too good”, in that it made the inventory of kennings appear as a static system. This impression was further strengthened through Meissner’s kenning catalogue (1921) and Fijestøl’s structuralist analysis of the kenning “system” (1974). In fact, however,

⁶ This is partly shown by Patria’s work on innovation and intertextuality, and partly by the fact that the majority of kennings are unique, meaning that the skalds must have memorised the canon and actively avoided the use of kennings found in earlier poetry (Wills 2021).

the kenning inventory had constantly been evolving, and only through Snorri's presentation did it come to appear as a closed system. When arranging the kennings in such a logical and accessible manner, Snorri was very much the prescriptive grammarian. Through her analysis of the term *nygerving*, however, Patria has uncovered an underlying tension between the grammarian and the skald. As a skald, Snorri knew that innovation was at the heart of the skaldic art, and at times, the skald broke through the strict grid imposed by the grammarian. This internal tension between native and Latin intellectual discourses is one of the features that makes Snorri's *Edda* into such a seemingly inexhaustible source of analytical challenges and new and fascinating insights.

Snorri's sources. Moving on to the question of Snorri's sources, this has been a fraught topic of debate for over a century, being intrinsically connected to whether his *Edda* may be used as a point of access to pagan perceptions or not. The debate has involved both Latin and vernacular sources. If Snorri drew heavily on Latin sources, his account may not be very trustworthy, and the same holds true if he manipulated his vernacular sources considerably or even invented his stories outright. A fundamental problem in this debate is that scholars have often been more prone to advance mutually exclusive claims than to devise ways of testing their relative merits. I begin with Latin.

Sources: Latin. Scholarly opinions here diverge drastically. Thus, for instance, Helgi Þorláksson argues that Snorri's knowledge of Latin was very rudimentary, whereas Matthias Teichert and Sverrir Tómasson present him as something of a scholar of Classics, notwithstanding the unlikelihood that such a person would have existed in thirteenth-century Iceland (Helgi Þorláksson 2014; Teichert 2013; Sverrir Tómasson 1997). In 1987, Margaret Clunies Ross presented a large study of *Skáldskaparmál*, arguing that it was deeply influenced by encyclopaedic and other Latin literature, and in 1993, Anthony Faulkes responded with a study claiming the opposite. Clunies Ross argued on the basis of general similarities, such as the use of the word *kenning* in religious discourse discussed above. Here, the main problem is that it is often difficult to evaluate whether apparent similarities are diagnostic of influence or not. Faulkes' response to Clunies Ross's study was of comparably general nature, but with an emphasis on dissimilarity rather than similarity. Faulkes noted that Snorri's style and attitudes are «totally Icelandic», indicating that he could not have read such twelfth-century Latin scholarship as some scholars have credited him with (Falkes 1997: 75). At face value, Faulkes' conclusion seems reasonable, but Snorri seems actively to have cultivated an image of a sealed Nordic cosmos, and under such circumstances, it is difficult to say what possible Latin analogues he may have chosen to suppress. Nonetheless, Faulkes has a point in doubting the likelihood that Snorri had read sources that were probably unknown in Iceland, and it is noteworthy that a number of later publications have not followed him in this regard (e.g. Teichert 2013; Malm 2009; Sverrir Tómasson 1997). In addition to Snorri's actively nativising approach, the

strength of the Old Norse poetic tradition may have supplied him with analytical categories comparable to but distinct from Latin ones. Kristján Árnason takes a balanced approach in this regard, exploring plausible Latin influences while also noting that Greek and Latin metrical terminology focused on form, whereas that of Snorri centres on function (e.g. μέτρον / *metrum*, roughly ‘measure’, versus *hátttr* ‘way, manner’, both today translated as ‘metre’ based on Classical tradition; Kristján Árnason 2013: 144-145). Kristján does not commit to either a primarily native or Latin perspective, and it would appear that such an open approach is best suited to accommodate the evidence (similarly de Pins 2013: 792-876).

The prologue to Snorri’s *Edda* obviously draws on Latin or Latin-derived sources, but even in this “easy” case, both sources and the interpretive framework remain elusive. Anglophone scholars have long tended to view the prologue as an expression of standard models such as the macrocosm-microcosm analogy and the argument from design (e.g. Dronke and Dronke 1977; Faulkes 1983), but as Gunnar Harðarson notes, it is in fact anything but standard on either account (Gunnar Harðarson 2016b). There is also a section on Troy in *Skáldskaparmál*, but both manuscript and linguistic evidence indicate that it has been interpolated, and the same may well be true of a short final section on Troy in *Gylfaginning* (Males 2021b: 123-125). Regarding the more challenging question of Latin sources to the remainder of the *Edda*, the present author in 2020 explored potential models among works widely used in instruction, under the assumption that these are more plausible sources of inspiration than texts with limited dissemination. The results were somewhat underwhelming. Regarding Snorri’s insistence on the use of consistent metaphors, I noted that Snorri was at odds with skaldic practice, and that the interference of the standard text on poetics up to Snorri’s day, Horace’s *Ars poetica*, was therefore likely (Males 2020: 121-124). Furthermore, Snorri probably modelled the opening of the commentary of *Háttatal* on Donatus’s *Ars minor* (or a comparable grammatical primer) (Males 2020: 125-129).

Perhaps other sources will in time be identified, but when dealing with a native speaker like Snorri, this is no easy task. Furthermore, as illustrated by Patria’s study of *nýgerving*, Snorri thought like a skald, even when attempting to create a strict, Latin-style taxonomy. Since this tension is identifiable, whereas Latin sources beyond the basic curriculum literature have so far proven elusive, it is possible that scholars’ efforts are better spent in exploring Latin-derived versus native perspectives, rather than Snorri’s use of specific Latin texts. Yet another observation may serve to illustrate this point.

In *Háttatal*, Snorri added a commentary to his own vernacular poem. In the Western tradition, commentary was for Latin, time-honoured authorities, and Snorri was thus an innovator both in composing a commentary on a vernacular text and, in particular, in applying it to his own work. (The Irish had preceded Snorri in the former aspect, but not the latter.) Only with Dante’s *Convivio* some 70-80 years later would another author employ this daring format. The fact that

Snorri did so suggests that for his technical description, he needed a type of text that neither the Latin nor the native tradition could offer. On the one hand, it needed to appear grammatical, in the sense of adhering to strict and detailed rules, and it thus had to be more “Latin” than the earlier skaldic discourse really was. On the other, it had to be based on actual skaldic conventions, which ruled out the use of any specific Latin model. Circumstance thus led Snorri to this innovation, which cannot be aptly described by reference to his models, since the absence of suitable models was what prompted the innovation in the first place. In a slightly less straightforward manner, this most likely holds true of Snorri’s *Edda* overall. There simply was no model that could serve his needs without considerable adaptation. As a result, he was at the same time highly innovative and staunchly traditional, and we must adjust our methods and expectations to this peculiar combination of characteristics.

Sources: Vernacular. In the debate on Snorri’s use of vernacular sources, too, claims and counterclaims have often been more prominent than attempts at assessing the relative merits of competing hypotheses. An inherent problem in the discussion is that it has largely centred on assumptions regarding lost sources, which are by definition difficult to test. In 1981, Roberta Frank took an important step in the direction of testing, comparing Snorri’s description of the mead of poetry-myth to references found in poetry. She argued that the name of the mythological being Kvasir, whose blood became the mead of poetry, as well those of the mythological vats, Són, Boðn and Óðrerir, were in fact common nouns in earlier poetry, meaning that this section of the myth was Snorri’s construct. In 2020, the present author reviewed her arguments (Males 2020: 148-164). In the case of Són and Boðn, Frank’s reading of earlier stanzas is possible, though not obviously superior to traditional interpretations. In the case of Kvasir, however, Frank takes *kvasis dreyri* to mean ‘ferment’s blood’, which she interprets as ‘mead’, here used metaphorically for ‘poetry’. This is not how skaldic references to poetry operate, however. When mead figures in such kennings, it always comes with a definer: ‘Óðinn’s mead’, ‘the mead of the gods’, and so on. By contrast, ‘mead’ simply means ‘mead’. In this instance, the myth is thus needed. In the case of Óðrerir, Frank omits a reference in *Hávamál* that clearly shows that it is the name of a vat, not a common noun. At least in Frank’s own formulation, her hypothesis is thus falsified, but her contribution is nonetheless substantial, in that she advocated detailed comparison between Snorri and his sources, enabling the scholar to produce sufficiently specific hypotheses to be susceptible to falsification. In earlier studies of Snorri’s poetic sources, such attempts have been rare, although Anne Holtsmark’s contrastive study of the poem *Haustlong* and Snorri’s rendition of its narrative deserves particular mention (Holtsmark 1950).

Taking my cue from Frank’s method, I explored the topic further in 2021. My results indicate that Snorri was selective in his quotations, in order to present an account sharing features with Biblical history, but which was also structurally

coherent in general. In her doctoral thesis, which is still in preparation, Yulia Osovtsova employs a similar approach and reaches more detailed results, in particular regarding Snorri's methods for achieving internal consistency from chaotic and partly contradictory sources. Comparable conclusions are also reached by James Parkhouse on the narrower topic of Snorri's presentation of Loki (Parkhouse 2021). Comparing Snorri's list of kennings for Loki with kennings preserved in the poetic corpus, Parkhouse notes that Snorri seems to have omitted positive in favour of negative ones, thus adapting Loki to his orderly mythological cosmos. Roughly the same method is also used by Daniel Sävborg in order to argue that Snorri inserted the proto-giant Ymir and the primaeval cow Auðhumbla into the creation account (Sävborg 2024a). Sävborg's hypothesis attributes more drastic interventions to Snorri than what I, Osovtsova and Parkhouse suggest, and it requires him to assume that Ymir in two of the three versions of the poem *Völuspá* is due to a later alteration. This is questionable on stemmatological grounds, but also because Ymir is a clear *lectio difficilior* from the perspective of the Christian culture of Snorri's day. It is thus doubtful whether Sävborg's analysis stands up to scrutiny, but as in the case of Frank's study, this does not detract from its value for knowledge production, since Sävborg's arguments are specific enough to allow for evaluation.

Sources: An Irish Story? With regard to vernacular sources, the possible Irish provenance of the story of Útgarða-Loki in *Gylfaginning* is of particular interest, as this might explain some unusual characteristics of this section. Rosemary Power explored the topic in 1985, and in 2013 Matthias Egeler discussed her study as an example of how cross-cultural influences may be studied with methodological rigour. As Egeler notes, Power's study had largely been bypassed in Old Norse scholarship, and it was thus only with the publication of his study that it entered the mainstream of scholarship on Snorri's *Edda* (Egeler 2013: 158 n. 25). The topic has occupied scholars for a long time, however. The *loci classici* are a study by Carl Wilhelm von Sydow (1910) and Finnur Jónsson's response to it (1921: 104-115). Finnur argued that the analogues presented by von Sydow were inconspicuous, but also that the episode was typically Norse, so that there was no reason to argue for outside influence. Power and Egeler demonstrate that the similarities are considerably greater than von Sydow had argued, thus meeting the first point of Finnur's critique, but they address the second only in passing, saying that the Útgarða-Loki episode lacks Old Norse analogues (Power 1985: 220; Egeler 2013: 160). They thus appear to claim the opposite of what Finnur does, which is confusing. After a brief presentation of the analogues, I will therefore discuss Old Norse references to the Útgarða-Loki episode.

Differences notwithstanding, the similarities between the story of Útgarða-Loki and an episode in *Feis Tighe Chonáin* ('The Feast of the House of Conán') are striking (Power 1985: 226-228). To mention just a few salient points: in *Feis Tighe Chonáin*, the hero and his company pursue a giant and encounter a young woman

who runs faster than all others. Having arrived at a pleasant house, an old woman temporarily turns the hero's companions into old men. After the hero has slept for a while, his host explains to him that all their experiences were allegories. The young woman was 'thought' (*Meanma*) and the old woman was 'old age' (*Críne*). The next morning, the house and all its inhabitants had disappeared. In *Gylfaginning*, the hero and his company encounter a giant, arrive at a wondrous house and compete against an incredibly fast boy whose name means 'thought' (*Hugi*) and an old woman (*Elli* 'old age'). The next morning, their host explains that they had been the objects of illusions and that the boy was indeed his thought and the old woman was old age. After this, the host and the house disappear.

We here see a remarkable combination of overlapping elements and personification allegory (*Meanma*, *Críne*; *Hugi*, *Elli*). Now that Power and Egeler have presented this evidence, Finnur's first point of critique, that the Irish analogues are not very striking, does not appear valid. The reason for the second difference of opinion, regarding whether there are internal Old Norse analogues to the *Útgarða-Loki* story, is less transparent. On closer inspection, it turns out that this in part depends on their relative emphasis on different parts of the story. Finnur focuses on the journey to *Útgarða-Loki*, whereas Power and Egeler mainly discuss events upon arrival. None of the scholars involved clarify this difference in emphasis, and their claims thus appear mutually exclusive.

In *Gylfaginning*, Þórr's journey serves as a prelude to the description of events at *Útgarða-Loki*'s. Three motifs on this journey are attested in early poetry: Þórr hides in the glove of a giant (*Lokasenna* 60; *Hárbarðsljóð* 26); Þórr is unable to untie a giant's knots (*Lokasenna* 62); one of Þórr's goats becomes lame and a farmer / giant pays for this with his children (*Hymiskviða* 37-38). By contrast, references to any part of the sojourn at *Útgarða-Loki*'s are more elusive and confined to the complex skaldic discourse. In Finnur's view, there was only one such reference, in a kenning in a stanza attributed to Kveld-Ulfr, where 'old age' is referred to as *Þórs fangvina* 'Þórr's female wrestling-friend' (Finnur Jónsson 1921: 112). A hiatus form in the stanza suggests that it is older than *c.* 1150⁷. If authentic, this is the oldest stanza in *Egils saga*, although it is cause for concern that the following stanza, which would be the second oldest, displays end-rhyme and thus seems to be spurious (Clunies Ross *et al.* 2007-, 5: 165). Authentic or not, the reference to *Elli* is unambiguous, and the *Útgarða-Loki* episode is thus not quite as isolated in the Old Norse tradition as it appears in Power's and Egeler's analysis.

In addition to this reference, Þorgeir Sigurðsson has proposed a reinterpretation of the kenning *fangboði forns Litar flotna* in Bragi's stanzas about Þórr's

⁷ The statement in Clunies Ross *et al.* (2007-: 5, 163), that odd verses in the stanza display irregular *skothendingar*, suggesting an early date, is not correct. The statement may refer to the instance of vocalic *hending* versus glide in the first verse, but this is conventional (*nú* : *eyju*).

fishing (stanza 5; Clunies Ross *et al.* 2007-: 3, 51). This kenning is traditionally interpreted as ‘the wrestling-challenger of the men of old Litr’, Litr being a giant and the wrestling-challenger of his men being Þórr. Þorgeir takes *litr* as a common noun, however, meaning ‘looks’, and ‘the old looks of men’ as Old Age (*Elli*), whose wrestling-challenger is Þórr (Þorgeir Sigurðsson, 2023: 178). Þorgeir notes that Litr is not otherwise known as the name of a giant, which speaks in favour of his interpretation⁸, and to this may be added that Þórr is normally a killer of giants and does not wrestle with them. Apart from the kenning *Þórs fangvina* in the stanza attributed to Kveld-Ulfr, this topic is otherwise found only in a fourteenth-century stanza attributed to Grettir: *fangvinr Hafli* ‘wrestling-friend of Hafli’ (Clunies Ross *et al.* 2007-: 5, 726; Males 2020: 270 n. 284). There is also a potential obstacle to Þorgeir’s interpretation, however. Unlike the kenning *Þórs fangvina*, we would here be dealing with wordplay: ‘old looks of men’ > *elli* ‘old age’ > *Elli*. Comparable wordplay is attested a few times in poetry postdating Bragi by more than a century, its closest analogues perhaps being kennings for ‘earth’ in Hallfrøðr vandroedaskáld’s *Hákonardrápa* (Males 2020: 49-51, 55). Assuming wordplay of similar complexity in the early poet Bragi as in the experimental poetry around Hákon jarl may seem daring. Still, the topic of wrestling speaks strongly in favour of Þorgeir’s interpretation. If this reference is accepted, the topic is attested in the earliest datable Old Norse poet. This does not rule out Irish influence, however, since Bragi has the first occurrence of an Irish loanword (*lung*).

If authentic and correctly interpreted, these references belong to an advanced skaldic register, whereas there are no traces of the events at Útgarða-Loki’s in narrative sources, such as the eddic poems⁹. In Saxo, a certain Thorkillus and his companions travel to Ugarthilocus, a giant whose hands and feet are in fetters. They extract a beard stub long as a spear from his cheek and go on their way (*Gesta Danorum*, VIII. 15.13). Apart from the names, the journey and the fact that Ugarthilocus is a giant, there are no conspicuous similarities to the story found in *Gylfaginning*.

Þórr’s journey to Útgarða-Loki is typical of this god, who often travels to encounter giants, whereas the use of personification allegory which dominates the Útgarða-Loki story proper is not. Consider, for instance, the following passage:

⁸ It may be noted that although Litr is not elsewhere attested as the name of a giant, it is found twice as that of a dwarf, in *Völuspá* 12 and Snorri’s prose in *Gylfaginning* (Faulkes 2005: 46). *Völuspá* 11-16 are likely interpolated, meaning that both attestations are late, but in any event, we do have some evidence that Litr belonged to the dwarf-giant continuum, offering some support for the traditional reading.

⁹ In addition to these, there are two references to Þórr’s wrestling match with Elli in *rimur* (*Mágus rimur* IV. 5-6; *Skikkju rimur* III. 1). The impact of Snorri’s *Edda* on the *rimur* was profound, however, and these references are therefore probably of limited importance for the evaluation.

En hitt var ok mikit undr um fangit er þú stótt svá lengi við ok fell eigi meir en á kné
 qðrum fœti er þú fekzk við *Ell*i, fyrir því at engi hefir sá orðit, ok engi mun verða
 ef svá gamall er at *elli* biðr, at eigi komi *ellin* qllum til falls. (Faulkes 2005: 43; my
 italics)

[And that too was a great wonder in the wrestling match that you held out for so
 long and did not fall more than onto one knee when you competed against *Old Age*,
 for there has been no one and will be no one, if he becomes old enough to experi-
 ence *old age*, that *old age* will not cause everyone to fall.] (my italics)

Such plain personification allegory, or *prosopopeia*, is never found in the tradi-
 tional mythological corpus and does not seem compatible with its tenor. For that
 reason, it may seem unlikely that any older poetic source that might have served
 as a source to this story ever existed. Why, then, is a lengthy section based on
 personification allegory found in *Gylfaginning*?

The hypothesis of external influence can explain why the episode is atypical,
 but not why Snorri would include such an episode when his overall method was to
 base his narrative on poetic sources. Neither Power nor Egeler addresses this prob-
 lem, but it is difficult to see how their hypothesis can be fully convincing without
 a plausible explanation of it. Unlike Finnur, Power, Egeler and other scholars
 treating the topic, I would suggest that it may be useful to treat the “journey” part
 of the episode separately, at least to some extent, since it has considerable support
 in older eddic poems and conforms to narrative patterns typical of Þórr, but also
 because its Irish analogues are less conspicuous than those of the “sojourn”. From
 the perspective of Old Norse tradition and Snorri’s method, it is thus only the “so-
 journ” that calls for an explanation.

In order to find one, one may consider whether the episode conforms to some
 known pattern of reception of mythology that may explain Snorri’s uncharacteris-
 tic behaviour. I would suggest that it does. I here allow myself to be speculative,
 my main point being that if we assume Irish influence, the resulting narrative must
 somehow have reached Snorri, and I believe it worthwhile to explore a scenario
 in which this may have happened. Although our knowledge of the use of tradi-
 tional stories in early mission is limited, we have evidence that the story of Þórr
 and the Midgard serpent was repurposed for preaching about God’s fight with the
 Leviathan, and some heroic lore appears to have been put to similar use (Males
 2020: 86-87; Ashman Rowe 2006; Neubauer 2019). The “sojourn” episode seems
 to conform to such a practice of repurposing of Þórr, since it has the character of
 a set of moral examples, showing that Þórr cannot ultimately overcome the forc-
 es of nature. This adaptation could have happened in, say, the tenth or eleventh
 century, when Irish-Norse contacts were close. If the references in *Kveld-Ulfr* and
Bragi are correctly dated and interpreted, the motif may even have been appro-
 priated in the ninth century. If so, the initial impulse would presumably not have
 been repurposing for Christian mission, though this may have happened later and

contributed to the survival of the story. Rather, the story would have served as a witty illustration of the limitations of Þórr's power, pointing to future events in Ragnarøk. Either way, it seems likely that the narrative would have been transmitted outside the poetic discourse, where personification allegory would be a bad fit. It would thus have reached Snorri as a piece of potentially useful lore about Þórr, but without a basis in poetry. It may still appear strange that he chose to include it, but I would suggest that he did so to provide a rift in the veil of pagan lies presented in *Gylfaginning*. In reality, the gods were not gods but humans, and as such, they were subjected to the forces of nature, just as everyone else (cf. Wellendorf's exploration of Snorri's primarily euhemeristic perspective discussed above). The allegorical story about Þórr allowed him to create such a rift.

It is for others to decide whether this outline of the background of the Útgarða-Loki episode is plausible, and in any event, the hypothesis would require further exploration in order to evaluate its merits. The late date of relevant Irish sources is a particular cause for concern. The main point of this discussion is to illustrate that Power's and Egeler's studies raise corollary questions that need to be addressed. This should not be understood as criticism of their work, but on the contrary, it is precisely because their studies render the hypothesis of influence that much stronger that its implications call for further investigation.

Sources: Lost compendia. In his 1982 monograph on Old Norse court poetry, Bjarne Fidjestøl suggested that the authors of kings' sagas may have drawn on compendia of skaldic poetry, but he thought it «hardly possible to test» this hypothesis (Fidjestøl 1982: 46). It seems likely that Fidjestøl would have taken a similar view on our ability to evaluate whether Snorri used such compendia in his work on *Skáldskaparmál*. It was therefore noteworthy when Lasse Mårtensson and Heimir Pálsson presented positive evidence to this effect in 2008. Their method was elegant, taking its starting point in the fact that suspension is used when a refrain is repeated in a consecutive manuscript text, such as *v.e.h.* for *vituð ér enn eða hvat* in *Völuspá*. Such drastic suspension would be incomprehensible unless the full text had first been given. Focusing on the Uppsala manuscript of Snorri's *Edda*, the authors found such suspension in Þjóðólfr Arnórsson's *Sexsteffa*, and more precisely in one of its refrains. The refrain is not found earlier in *Skáldskaparmál*, however, and the suspensions thus presumably indicate that the author was working from a full exemplar of the poem. The resulting incomprehensible text was corrected in the other manuscripts but retained in U. This suggests that Snorri worked with written copies of at least some of the poems that he used. Subsequently, Klaus Johan Myrvoll has investigated the presence of Icelandicisms in the Norwegian king's saga *Fagrskinna*, noting that these are much more prevalent in the poetry than in the prose, and that the overlap with the poetic corpus in *Heimskringla* is remarkable (Myrvoll 2023: 99-106). Based on chronology and context, Myrvoll concludes that the most likely explanation is that the author drew on poetic compendia supplied to him by none other than Snorri during

his first journey to Norway. Thus, in spite of Fidjestøl's misgivings, evidence is now mounting that Snorri worked from poetic compendia. What was needed was a methodological innovation, since Fidjestøl did not relate the question to palaeography and orthography, which has now turned out to be a fruitful approach.

The Uppsala Edda (U). The Uppsala manuscript of Snorri's *Edda* differs considerably from the other three main manuscripts containing the entire work (R, T and W), and the reasons for this divergence have occupied scholars for a long time. In 2012 Daniel Sävborg noted that sections in U that feature a particularly terse style, which scholars have sometimes taken to reflect a more original version, are interspersed with sections of similar length and style to the text in the other witnesses. Since all witnesses agree in the wordier sections, whereas they diverge in the terser ones, the richer style was apparently first shared by all branches, whereas a copyist at one or more removes from the preserved Uppsala manuscript abbreviated sections of the work, retaining crucial information but deleting what was not needed to "get the gist". As Sävborg notes, we have evidence of a similar procedure in other texts through the hands of Haukr Erlendsson and his "main secretary" in the early fourteenth-century Hauksbók. In short, Sävborg first presented the only plausible explanation of the facts and then empirical evidence that such dynamics are indeed attested. This classic bone of contention within scholarship on Snorri's *Edda* is thus no longer contended.

In the same year, Heimir Pálsson's edition of the *Uppsala Edda* appeared, with a translation by Anthony Faulkes. Both with regard to structure and content, the *Uppsala Edda* is so different from the RTW version that it is difficult to gain a representative impression of it through a traditional, text-critical edition. An older edition by Anders Grape, Gottfrid Kallstenius and Olof Thorell (1962-1977) is excellent, but in some respects more unwieldy and difficult to come by. Heimir's edition thus facilitates scholarship on Snorri's *Edda* considerably. It is somewhat unfortunate, however, that Sävborg's observations were not made in time to be incorporated into the introduction. Instead, Heimir is thoroughly invested in the view that U represents the first draft of the work¹⁰. Thus, for instance, he states that «There are simply too many differences between the two versions of important events like the death of Baldr or the theft of Iðunn's apples for it to be possible for the two versions to have come about by the shortening of one or the lengthening of the other» (Heimir Pálsson 2012: lv-lvi). In fact, Heimir compares only the two versions of the latter motif in any detail, and his evaluation does not seem to be based on generally accepted principles of textual criticism. Thus, for instance, he stresses that the R version says that Þjazi snatched up both of the ox's thighs, whereas in the U version he took only

¹⁰ In Sävborg's words: «The book should, although it also contains a valuable edition of the U text itself, primarily be described as a monograph arguing in favour of this view [that U is a first draft]» (Sävborg 2024b: 310 n. 7).

one of them. On closer inspection, the difference between the two text is easily explained as the result of misreading. R has «leggr upp þegar it fyrsta lær oxans tvau» ‘and immediately first lays up the two thighs of the ox’. Until the reader comes to the final «tvau», this clause would seem to mean ‘and immediately lays up the first thigh of the ox’. This appears to have prompted a reanalysis, which together with the U redactor’s penchant for abbreviation has resulted in «tók annat uxalærit» ‘took one of the thighs of the ox’ in U (Heimir Pálsson 2012, liii-liv). Far from being impossible, abbreviation easily explains the difference, which is fully in line with known scribal tendencies to trivialise and to read only a few words at a time. Despite Heimir’s claim to the contrary, his examples are thus compatible with Sävborg’s analysis, and in this instance even serve to strengthen it.

Recently, Sävborg published another study on a closely related topic. The article discussed above focuses on abbreviation of prose narrative and pertains mainly to *Gylfaginning*, whereas in 2024, Sävborg turned to the organisation of the text in *Skáldskaparmál*. In this section, the main difference between the versions is that in RTW, narrative and examples of kennings and stanzas are intertwined, portions of narrative preceding examples pertaining to it, whereas in U, these narratives are set apart and are instead found in the end of *Gylfaginning* and *Skáldskaparmál*. In this instance, Sävborg devised another method to evaluate which version is prior, focusing on inconsistencies and leaving out W, due to some further reworking that makes it less suited to his study. In some instances, the text in U mentions what has been said previously or what will follow, which turns out to be consistent with RT but misleading in U, and in one instance, a stanza is found only once in RT but twice in U, without serving any obvious function the second time it is quoted. All these inconsistencies can be explained through the transposition of the narrative sections, and the structure of *Skáldskaparmál* in U is thus clearly secondary.

Sävborg’s studies leave scholars much better equipped to understand the transmission of Snorri’s *Edda*. It should be noted, however, that even though U is secondary to the RTW version in terms of abbreviation and organisation, Sävborg does not question its text-critical value. In many instances, U’s readings need to be taken into account. Furthermore, not all aspects of U’s organisation need be secondary. Thus, for instance, the fact that several longer poems are missing in U may be relevant to the evaluation of whether Snorri originally included them, since the U redactor seems mainly to have abbreviated and reorganised the prose. Something similar may be said of other likely interpolations, such as the first chapter of *Gylfaginning* and the chapter on Troy in *Skáldskaparmál*, both missing in U. These sections are in prose, but the U redactor would typically abbreviate while retaining factual content, not delete portions of the narrative. In terms of organisation, then, U may be both our least and our most faithful witness, depending on the question at hand. Similarly, the U scribe clearly had the worst understanding of poetry among the scribes of the main witnesses, but poor scribal understanding can often leave valuable text-critical clues, rendering U indispensable in this regard as well.

3. Poetry

A considerable advance for the study of the poetry contained in the grammatical corpus was the publication of the bipartite third volume of *Skaldic Poetry in the Scandinavian Middle Ages* (Clunies Ross *et al.* 2007-). This is now the standard edition of the poetry in the grammatical corpus. Of course, debates on editorial choices and hypotheses will continue, especially since the first part of the volume contains some of the most challenging and interesting poetry in the corpus. Unlike Finnur Jónsson's older standard edition of the skaldic corpus, however, the editors of *Skaldic Poetry* explain their choices, which makes it that much easier to test their validity. This alone is a considerable advance to the field, and in tandem with the project's database, the new edition is a powerful tool that will continue to engender valuable research for the foreseeable future.

Two monographs are also worthy of particular mention. In 2001, Guðrún Nordal brought the connection between twelfth-century poetry and thirteenth-century scholarship to the fore in her *Tools of Literacy*. A few years later, Margaret Clunies Ross published *A History of Old Norse Poetry and Poetics* (2005), which also explores the continuities between the poetic tradition and grammatical literature. With the more general scope implied by the title *A History*, Clunies Ross's book has served to make Guðrún's holistic approach into a natural starting point to subsequent scholars.

Guðrún and Clunies Ross discuss the connection between poetry and grammatical literature, and in a forthcoming article, the present author explores comparable perspectives by analysing a twelfth-century poem that may be seen as a precursor to the grammatical treatises. This is the so-called *Icelandic Rune Poem*. This poem was long thought to be later than the *Norwegian Rune Poem*, the latter usually being dated to sometime in the thirteenth century. There are clear metrical and semantic signs that the Norwegian poem is modelled on the Icelandic one, however, and the use of the Icelandic poem in a runic inscription of *c.* 1200 dates it to the twelfth century. The study of the links between the *Anglo-Saxon*, *Icelandic* and *Norwegian Rune Poems* involves a range of detailed parameters, and a few salient points must therefore suffice here.

Various indications show that none of the three poems originally contained the names of the runes, but only their shapes. Each stanza thus constituted a riddle whose solution was the name of the rune. This means that all three poems must have been intended for visual representation of the runes with an accompanying exposition through the known medium of Latin script. Oral composition is thus ruled out, and instead, we are dealing with grammatical exercises. This format is impossible in Latin, since the names of the Latin letters are not words in the language. The adaptation of a Latin model to this format thus called for considerable ingenuity, which suggests that it happened only once. A likely time and place for such an innovation is ninth-(or perhaps early tenth-)century England, where similar texts were known in Latin, and where grammatical preoccupation with runes

was prevalent, so much so that it spread from there to the Continent. These pre-conditions were not present in twelfth-century Iceland, where Latin-script literacy was still in its infancy. This and other evidence discussed in the article indicates a line of influence *Anglo-Saxon* > *Icelandic* > *Norwegian Rune Poem*.

From 1GT, we know of grammatical preoccupation with runes in twelfth-century Iceland, and in a note in Codex Wormianus, we learn that some kind of grammatical “arrangement” of the runes was composed by Ari fróði (1067/1068-1148). Since Ari was active shortly before the composition of 1GT and the First Grammatician clearly reacted against some such initiative, the attribution of the *Icelandic Rune Poem* to him seems plausible. At least, the poem was clearly composed in the twelfth century, most likely in the first half, before 1GT.

In light of the modern name, the *Icelandic Rune Poem*, it may seem remarkable that the note in Wormianus says that Ari had *sett* ‘arranged’ the runes, rather than using the verb *ort* ‘composed’, which typically refers to the composition of poetry. A comparison between witnesses shows, however, that each stanza in the original “arrangement” had the following structure:

ƿ [= fé] er frænda róg	Wealth is trouble among relatives
ok flæðar viti	and fire of the sea [kenning for ‘gold’]
ok grafseiðs gata.	and path of the serpent [kenning for ‘gold’].
<i>Aurum. fylkir</i>	<i>Aurum. Ruler</i> (beginning with <i>f</i>)

In other words, each rune was treated in a stanza followed by an approximate Latin translation and a word beginning in the sound-value of the rune. This is, in fact, not simply a poem, but an “arrangement”. Not merely a poem, but not yet a treatise, it is an interesting early hybrid pointing towards later developments, in this case notably the Latin-derived treatment of runes in 3GT. Like other advances discussed in this article, the redating of the *Icelandic Rune Poem* and the identification of the line of influence between the three rune poems relies on replacing vague arguments with criteria susceptible to testing, such as metre and grammar.

4. Final Words

By way of conclusion, I would like to emphasise two points. The first is that all contributions discussed here share one fundamental characteristic: they attempt to evaluate the merits of competing hypotheses by recourse to some kind of testing¹¹. In several instances, the study under discussion is the first to introduce this *sine qua non* of probabilistic evaluation into the debate. It is worth emphasising that

¹¹ It should be noted that this is true also of editions, which necessarily involve the testing of a wide range of hypotheses in order to arrive at a plausible representation of the author’s, archetype’s or scribe’s intentions.

this approach is feasible not only when drawing on criteria traditionally perceived as “scientific”, such as linguistic and metrical ones, but also in relation to textual content. Thus, for instance, Jonas Wellendorf has demonstrated that Holtsmark’s hypothesis regarding Snorri’s interpretive framework lacks credible support in the source text. Perhaps even more conspicuously, Daniel Sävborg has twice clarified the underlying causes of differences between the U and RT redactions of Snorri’s *Edda* by simply reading the text, rather than focusing on the minute variants typically favoured by textual critics. It is encouraging to see such literary perspectives being enrolled in the service of knowledge production.

Second, it is noteworthy that the advances in our understanding of Snorri’s *Edda* are so great, even though this text had already received much more scholarly attention than all the others combined. Apparently, the potential for advances is not related in any straightforward way to the amount of scholarship that has gone into a field of study. Rather, it depends on scholars’ willingness to subject their hypotheses to scrutiny and their methodological ingenuity in devising new tests, in combination with the characteristics of the object under study. Especially when Snorri’s *Edda* is explored with an eye to the poetic corpus on which it draws, it would seem that the object of study is so rich and complex that it will simply keep yielding new insights.

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